

SITE GS/SPHINX	DATE 7/16/79	AREA NE	SQUARE N3/W1	PAGE
 Feature No.	Coordinates:		Levels	
			Top: ≈ 10.64	Bottom: ≈ 10.58
	DIMENSIONS			
Diameter:		Width: ≈ 42 cm	Length: ≈ 30 cm	Depth: 6 cm

Locus	Mat.	Color	Hard.	Consis.	Pottery	Inclusions	
1	CLAY	BROWN to TAN	PACKED	Somewhat Rubby on breaking due to limestone small particles But matrix fine to powdery on drying	T O	Lm ✓ small frags, particles	Gp
						Gr ✓ 1 cluster very small chips	Char ✓ few spots
						Do	
					D	Ba	
						Al	
						Other	
2	GYPSUM w Limestone Frag	BUFF to WHITE	Packed	Rubby	T O	Lm ✓ frags 1	Gp
						Gr ✓ 1 small chip	Char ✓ Few spots
						Do	
					D	Ba	
						Al	
						Other	
2a	GYPSUM (w clay mix?)	YELLOW	COMPACT	Fine	T	Lm ✓ 2	Gp
						Gr	Char
						Do	
					D	Ba	
						Al	
						Other	
○					T	Lm	Gp
						Gr	Char
						Do	
					D	Ba	
						Al	
						Other	
○					T	Lm	Gp
						Gr	Char
						Do	
					D	Ba	
						Al	
						Other	

PHOTOGRAPH	Color: Roll/ 4	No./ 12, 13	B&W: Roll/ 3	No./ 27, 28
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DRAWN	Area Plan: 1:20	Feature Plan: 1:10	Sections: 2; E-W, AND N-S
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REMARKS; INTERPRETATION: 1 Large (9x6x5 cm) to very small frags, particles - see sections
 2 1 large frag (9x5.5x3 cm) to small particles

Question whether 2a diff. from 2. If so whether ①-② and C22 itself interrupts 2a. See note on section.